

VALKYRIES

D1.9 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

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A/1	19/01/2023	5	Comments from general project review consolidated report are addressed. New text and changes from previous version are highlighted in yellow for easy identification. Dissemination KPIs table has been updated.

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1. Executive Summary

As the project communication and dissemination with interested parties is of prominent importance, VALKYRIES is committed to address all requirements that shall drive an effective delivery of results to main stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle embracing the following actions:

- Definition of a unified communication strategy grounded on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).
- Identification of key stakeholders and tailored dissemination strategies with awareness of their contribution to the project.
- Identification of the official communication channels along with branding requirements in a variety of formats.
- Definition of both project-wide and individual dissemination plans with specific targets.

This deliverable analyses the role of communication and dissemination activities as project-wide coordinated endeavours committed to maximize the impact of VALKYRIES, which lead to draw a baseline of performance indicators and different strategies to engage key stakeholders in the dissemination and communication initiatives undertaken from the consortium. All these to come up with tailored plans to reach wider targeted audiences via suitable communication channels, fostering also the interaction with relevant parties of the first responders' sector, as broadly documented in the forthcoming sections of this document.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Deliverable Id: D1.9

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D1.9

Name of lead participant: Indra (IND)

Name of Contributors: All partners

Type: Report (R)

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

Proposed Classification Level: Non-Restricted

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Linked project Work Package: WP1 - Project Management and Communication

Linked project tasks: T1.3 - Consultation Strategy and Liaison with European/national authorities / T1.4 - Dissemination strategy

Action: Design

Status: First Release

Document Layout: VALKYRIES official template

Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions. Deliverable D1.9 is framed into the project tasks T1.3 and T1.4, having the purpose to document the defined communication & dissemination strategies. The document also reports all actions accounted in the reporting period from M1 to M6 of the project, as several partners undergone efforts to disseminate their involvement in VALKYRIES among different audiences.

3. Document and Project scope

3.1. Project Overview

The increasing frequency and intensity of natural and human-made disasters [1]-[4] require policies aimed at tackling these risks through preventive, preparedness, response and recovery actions. Increasing the resilience of infrastructures, ecosystems and society in EU is an important strand of disaster risk management work.

It is from this need that VALKYRIES was born, a project co-financed by the European Union (EU) under the framework of the H2020 program. It is within the field of security, specifically in disaster-resilient societies under the topic *Pre-normative research and demonstration for disaster-resilient societies: First aids vehicles deployment, training, maintenance, logistic and remote centralized coordination means*.

The project will develop a methodology for tracking and analysing the needs for standardisation and certification harmonisation as regards the tools for supporting EU disaster resiliency. Specifically, it will develop, integrate and demonstrate capabilities for enabling immediate and coordinated emergency response, including for search and rescue, security and health, in scenarios of natural/provoked catastrophes with multiple victims, with special application in cases in several regions or countries.

In order to develop the project, a multidisciplinary consortium has been created with key partners from industry (large companies and SMEs), universities, research centres and end users, which jointly have defined a series of work streams and international and cross-sectorial use cases that give the project great value.

3.2. Communication and Dissemination concepts and relevance

All Horizon 2020 projects are contractually obliged to communicate the project and its activities by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in a strategic and effective manner and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange, as stated in the project's Model Grant Agreement (Article 38).

Beyond this contractual obligation, the consortium is strongly aware of the need for this type of activities in order to guarantee the greatest possible visibility of the project, its integration with the current and future mechanisms, procedures and standards of the first responders and, above all, make a real impact on the future of the Security of European civil societies.

To achieve these purposes, not only the design and development of exceptional technical solutions is enough, but also a robust design and implementation of a communication strategy and dissemination of the results and achievements of the project.

Communication and dissemination concepts

Sometimes there is an overlap between communication and dissemination concepts and activities. Thus, in order to correctly develop communication and dissemination strategies we need to have a clear idea about the meaning of both concepts and what do they entail. The following definitions are the European Commission's official ones:

- **Communication** means to “call attention of multiple audiences about your research (in a way that they can be understood by non-specialists audiences)” [5].

- **Dissemination** means “sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers. By sharing your research results with the rest of the scientific community, you are contributing to the progress of science in general” [6].

In conclusion, both communication and dissemination activities have the main objective of advertising and propagating the project and its results, differentiating themselves in the target audiences to which these activities are directed. In other words, communication activities are aimed at a more general and non-specialized public, so the information must be transmitted clearly and avoiding technicalities, and dissemination activities are aimed at an audience specialized in the area and, therefore, the information transmitted may use technical and scientific language.

3.3. Deliverable objectives

This document applies to the project Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters (VALKYRIES) funded under the Grant Agreement of the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme tendering conditions. This deliverable takes part of work package 1 (WP1), which drives the project coordination, risk management, quality of assurance and other governance procedures as well as all coordinated actions needed to generate impact from the project’s vision and results via communication activities towards a wider transference and presence on cross-border and cross-sectorial disasters. The Consortium plans to conduct a communication and dissemination strategy that among others, covers the following actions:

- Creation of a personal branding for the project and its promotion
- Effective dissemination of results to target audiences via suitable communication channels.
- Organization of high-level workshops which includes general, legal and ethical, standardization and demonstration workshops.
- Interaction with partnerships and other projects and initiatives active in the first responders and civil security areas.

Deliverable D1.9 is directly linked with the project task T1.4 covering the communication & dissemination strategy and T1.3 Consultation Strategy and Liaison with European/national authorities. From the project standpoint, the main goal is to have a common framework to drive the proper communication channels in favour of a more efficient dissemination of the project results to the targeted audiences. Common guidelines drawn by the consortium drive the planning and execution of a wide range of initiatives committed to boost the dissemination of VALKYRIES results.

4. Communication Strategy

Communication is central for achieving the expected impact of the VALKYRIES project. The Consortium will perform the required communication activities to meet this purpose. The following goals will guide the communication activities of VALKYRIES to reach this main objective effectively:

1. **Communicate the benefits of the project results**, including their strong potential business impact in the creative industries sector, clearly and effectively.
2. **Establish a two-way communication with the target audiences** defined in Section 4.1. The Consortium aims to get feedback from target audiences, mainly from potential end-users, in an open dialogue to ensure a transparent, interactive research and innovation process that will lead to a strong global market impact.
3. **Foster the uptake of the VALKYRIES results** and their further use by the target business users.

These goals will be achieved through a set of communication activities that will be guided by two main principles: a) their effectiveness in reaching the target audiences; b) their return on investment and cost-effectiveness regarding the expected impacts. For implementing these principles, VALKYRIES will pursue a dynamic communication planning approach based on KPIs and target values (See section 4.5). VALKYRIES' communication activities are summarized in Table 5 and include the promotion of the VALKYRIES concepts and results through inter-project concertation, scientific publications, workshops, industry booths at significant events, as well as the project's Web Portal and complementary social media activities. VALKYRIES will be proactively communicating with target audiences in the EU and beyond from the outset of the project.

4.1. Target Audience

The target audience has been divided into two main groups: internal and external audience. The former refers to the actors that are directly involved in the project and between whom the information must flow in a clear and transparent manner. The second group corresponds to all public outside the project and whose interest is intended to awake.

Internal Audience

The internal audience includes:

- Consortium partners (Industries, SMEs, Research organizations and End users)
- External advisory board
- European Commission

External Audience

The external audience includes:

- General public
- Industry
- Research community and experts
- First responders and End users
- Standardization bodies
- Stakeholders

- Public actors

4.2. Key Messages

The messages conveyed by VALKYRIES will be adapted to the specific external audience as well as the communication material and content. Below we show a list of key messages detected to be spread among the external audience.

- What are the main problems detected when a disaster occurs on the border of a country?
- What are the first responders' needs?
- What is VALKYRIES?
- How does it affect you?
- What can VALKYRIES do for you?
- What is SIGRUN?
- What will be demonstrated in the cross-border and cross-sectorial demonstration scenarios?
- How the project's use cases will demonstrate advances over the current state of the art?
- What are the benefits of becoming involved in VALKYRIES?
 - Building partnerships
 - Learning about policies and funding
 - Engaging to create European investment opportunities and obtain funding for future joint projects

4.3. Communication Tools

In this section we describe the different actions and tools the Consortium is currently using and those that are planned to be used to achieve the VALKYRIES' communication objectives. They are mainly aimed at communicating at least the key messages specified above to the external and internal audiences. All these activities are summarized in Table 5.

4.3.1. Project Identity

4.3.1.1. Logo

As part of the creation of its own identity for VALKYRIES, a representative logo of the concept and origin of the selected name has been designed. According to the Norse Mythology, the Valkyries were female figures who choose those who may die in battle and those who may live (referring to their etymological meaning). Another attribution to the VALKYRIES was to lead warriors in their battle, training healing or reanimating them after a preparedness day. Based on this, the logo shown in Figure 1 was designed.

Figure 1 - VALKYRIES' logo

The logo will be used for all project-related internal and external activities such as deliverables, presentations, workshop invitations, letters, posters, information material and advertising material. The logo is also present on the VALKYRIES' website and social media accounts on Twitter and LinkedIn. The VALKYRIES logo can be published on partners own websites.

4.3.1.2. Documentary Templates

A set of PowerPoint and Word templates have been designed following the graphic line of the project (See Figure 3 and Figure 4). This will ensure a consistent and unified image that can be used for presentations and publications made by consortium members. These templates will enable the audience to identify the project immediately.

All presentations given by VALKYRIES' Consortium partners should use the approved PowerPoint template. In the same way, all delivered document should use the approved Word template.

As part of the EC obligations documentary and visual material delivered under this project should contain EU logo together with the following statement:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101020676

Figure 2 - EU logo and statement

The image shows a Word document template for VALKYRIES. The left page is the cover page, featuring the VALKYRIES logo at the top, followed by the document title 'D.X.X Document Title'. Below this are fields for 'Reference Number: NUMBER', 'Ed/Rev: edition/revision', 'Main Contributor: PARTNER NAME', and 'Other Contributors: PARTNER NAMES'. At the bottom, there is a 'Date: XX/XX/202X' field. The right page shows a table of contents with sections like 'Editors', 'Contributors', 'Document Changes Record', and 'Content'. The 'Content' section lists 'Section 1', 'Section 2', and 'Section 3', each with a 'Subsubsection' and a page number '2'.

Figure 3 - VALKYRIES' Word template

Figure 4 - VALKYRIES' PowerPoint template

4.3.1.3. Website

A website has been created and will be used as the main channel for communication throughout the project: www.valkyries-h2020.eu. It consists of an open access external, public-facing platform to showcase the project objectives, aims, work areas, relevant news and developments, social media links and project results and deliverables. All VALKYRIES' events will be publicized on the webpage with enough time in advance when the event is open to the public to encourage maximum participation and attendance. In the case of a restricted internal event, the news will be given once it is finished.

All partners are encouraged to share a link to www.valkyries-h2020.eu on their institutional websites as well as when public presentations and conferences are given.

The website will be updated monthly with relevant news, posts, press releases and events information. There is a contact email (info@valkyries-h2020.eu) available for the website users to facilitate contact with the consortium and request additional information about the project if desired.

The website complies with current legislation. It makes the legal notice and privacy policy of the website available to the user. In addition, it has undergone a security audit with a favourable rating for both the web service and the hosting server. Finally, in order to upload all the multimedia files of events, conferences, etc. that include the presence of natural persons to the web, the corresponding image declaration of consents have been compiled.

4.3.1.4. Social Media

Nowadays, social networks are extremely important and powerful tools for spreading information and reach a general public audience. VALKYRIES will use social media to ensure the project is widely communicated and that the need of this kind of project is well understood.

Sometimes the need to improve and invest in the civil security of citizens is relegated to the background, which is why using this type of platform to raise awareness among the population is of special importance for this consortium. Being able to carry the VALKYRIES message from a young audience to an older one. The aim of the social media strategy will be to build an engaged community.

The Twitter account: <https://twitter.com/ValkyriesH2020>

Twitter is dedicated to VALKYRIES-related news, will also be used to disseminate project results. Twitter will be used to communicate with our target audience. Partners are encouraged to tag the project as @ValkyriesH2020, when they attend events to publicise VALKYRIES. It will also be used to announce the latest news about the project.

The LinkedIn account: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/valkyries-h2020/?viewAsMember=true>

LinkedIn is mainly used for professional networking, including employers posting jobs and job seekers posting their CVs. It will be used as a forum for sharing information about VALKYRIES.

4.3.2. Newsletters, Fact sheets, Posters

A newsletter will be used to inform stakeholders about project developments. At least two newsletters per year will be issued. The first newsletter will be released in M7-M8. Consortium members are encouraged to include the VALKYRIES newsletter in their institutional newsletters and communication documents in order to increase local coverage. The e-newsletter will be created and disseminated through the network of all partners and on the website, including the outreach to relevant networks.

A fact sheet is currently being designed to be used during conferences and events and provide easily accessible information about VALKYRIES. In addition, posters, brochures and flyers will be created when needed to be presented on conferences and events. All partners are encouraged to disseminate this material when appropriate.

4.3.3. Press releases

Press releases will be used to increase awareness and disseminate information about the project with relevant stakeholders. More importantly, they will showcase the progress and the results obtained during the project development. At least two press releases per year will be issued. Press releases should be also published on consortium partners' websites.

During this first six months, VALKYRIES has gained attention from the general audience, present in several press releases where the aims and project envisioned capabilities have taken prominence. Table 1 provide evidence of VALKYRIES presence on digital media accordingly.

Source	URL
Indra's corporate website	https://www.indracompany.com/en/indra/valkyries-harmonization-pre-standardization-equipment-training-tactical-coordinated-procedures
Novotec's corporate website	https://www.novotec.es/global/es/news/novotec-participa-en-el-proyecto-europeo-valkyries-para-la-gestion-del-riesgo-de-catastrofes
ISEMI's corporate website	https://www.isemi.sk/en_GB/aktivity/
TASSICA's corporate website	https://www.tassica.com/index.php/sala-de-prensa/tassica-emergency-training-reseach-s-a-forma-p
AES	A press release presenting the SP-PT use case has been published by AES (Asociación Española de empresas de Seguridad). https://www.aesseguridad.es/boletin/80/index.html#features/

Table 1 - Press releases

4.3.4. Conferences and events, including trade shows and exhibitions

Industry and other non-scientific conferences will be excellent platforms to disseminate the project findings and start direct conversations with target audiences, particularly events related to security and health. The Consortium aims to get speaking slots and co-host VALKYRIES workshops at some of the conferences shown in Table 2. Moreover, the VALKYRIES Consortium will also show project results at fairs and congresses to increase awareness and stakeholder engagement.

Event/Forum	Main communication aspects
DG ECHO events (Civil Protection Forum) and additional EC events (DG CLIMA, DG ENV, JRC)	The EU Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations periodically organizes events targeting all audiences, from public diffusion (Info days, Volunteering, raising awareness) up to experts (European Civil Protection Forum, regional workshops, etc.).
Research Workshops of the International Federation of Red	The International Conference for decision-makers to discuss the world's most pressing humanitarian issues and adopt resolutions that

Event/Forum	Main communication aspects
Cross and Red Crescent Societies	guide future humanitarian action, international humanitarian law (IHL) and legal frameworks for disaster management.
The International Emergency Management Society (TIEMS) events	TIEMS activities comprise international conferences, workshops and exhibitions task force groups of experts from TIEMS international group of experts, and TIEMS academy providing international education, training and certification programs.
European Commission Community of User events	Meeting point of for the different “EU research families,” namely various programmes of DG RTD, DG CNECT, and DG HOME, as well as the Joint Research Centre (JRC).
European Civil Protection Forum	Gathers representatives from the European civil protection community, first-line responders, European institutions, etc. to discuss the current developments in the Union Civil Protection Mechanism framework and put forward new ideas.
Security Standardisation Research Conference	Research on security standardisation, including, but not restricted to, work on cryptographic techniques, security management, security evaluation criteria, security policy, network security, privacy and identity management, smart cards and RFID tags, biometrics, security modules, and industry-specific security standard.
International Disaster and Risk Conference (IDRC)	World’s leading conferences on integrative risk management, gathering business leaders, decision-makers, practitioners, UN-, IO- & NGO-agents, and scientists that share and discuss new findings and experiences about the broad spectrum of risks societies are facing today.
International Conference on Preparedness & Response to Emergencies & Disasters	This conference will provide an opportunity for professionals from around the world to share the latest findings and new experiences concerning health system readiness for disasters and emergencies of all types.
Military Communications and Information Systems Conference (MilCIS)	The event facilitates a continuing dialogue between the Department of Defence employees, contractors, industry and researchers to discuss current and developing technological capabilities, project initiatives, and operational requirements.
International Conference on Dependable Systems and Networks	CORE A. Fusion between dependability and security research, understanding the need to simultaneously fight against accidental faults, intentional cyber-attacks, design errors, and unexpected operating conditions. It is also providing fruitful ground for academia and industry interaction.
Computer Privacy and Data Protection (CPDP)	Computer Privacy and Data Protection is the leading annual conference on privacy and data protection. VALKYRIES aims at regularly holding panels to discuss its advances and main issues publicly.
SEGUREX	SEGUREX is the most important security fair organised in Portugal. EDGE will present results of VALKYRIES to potential customers and stakeholders.
MILIPOL PARIS	The MILIPOL Paris is one of the largest trade fairs for safety. International exhibitors show the latest trends, techniques and equipment in the industry. EDGE will present results of VALKYRIES to

Event/Forum	Main communication aspects
	potential customers and stakeholders, seeking to expand its international customer base.
European Emergency Medicine Congress	Annual international congress of the European Society for Emergency Medicine (EUSEM). The Consortium aims to disseminate and to discuss the results of VALKYRIES in this forum.
EMS Europe	Annual European Emergency Medical Services Congress (EMS). The Consortium aims to disseminate and to discuss the results of VALKYRIES in this forum.
XXXII SEMES National Congress	The Spanish Society of Emergency Medicine (SEMES) annually organizes a congress with great repercussion both in Spain and Portugal. This congress would provide a great opportunity for the communication and dissemination of the VALKYRIES project among health personnel.

Table 2 - Selection of targeted conferences and events

In addition, VALKYRIES should participate in different events in order to promote the project and to attract interested parties. This should be discussed with the Project Coordinator to ensure a unified approach.

4.3.5. Communication between VALKYRIES' consortium partners

In daily work, partners will share information and get in contact via email, telephone and videoconference.

A monthly checkpoint teleconference has been set up for all partners (at least one representative per partner) to take part and update on work packages, tasks, deliverables and detection of potential risks and delays. In addition, a set of relevant workshops have been scheduled (see section 5.1).

Document management

For the management of the documentation and its storage, a repository has been enabled in a private group on Microsoft Sharepoint to which all the members of the consortium have access. The definition of how the project documents should be formatted, the collaborative work methodology on the platform, the deliverables submission process to the EC, the repository folder structure and the writing language, is specified in the document "VALKYRIES Document Management". This document has been approved by the consortium and can be found in [Annex A – Documentation Management](#).

Satisfaction survey

In order to monitor the quality and level of satisfaction of the partners with the workshops and plenary meetings that are developed throughout the project, a satisfaction survey has been generated and it is distributed to partners at the end of the last session or in subsequent days.

Depending on the conditions in which these events are held (fully face-to-face, fully virtual or semi-face-to-face), this survey will be distributed either in physical format (survey printed on paper) or in electronic format (Office forms).

The template used for these surveys is included in [Annex B – Event Satisfaction Survey](#) of this document.

4.4. Communication Strategies

Internal Strategies

Awareness will be raised amongst consortium partners, EAB and interested stakeholders. All these actors are encouraged to spread VALKYRIES-related communications. This will help to reach a great number of European countries and public.

External Strategies

At European level, the European Commission produces a number of communication articles including the Horizon magazine, Research*EU magazine, Research*EU Focus magazine and newsletters. The consortium have already approached these channels [7] and we will continue to exploiting them.

The organization of workshops, round tables and conferences, among others, will allow us to interact with the audience, collect ideas and opinions from a wide variety of stakeholders from many different sectors and regions across Europe.

Attending other related conferences, workshops and events will allow us to detect synergies and potential liaisons with other EU projects. This could simply be as a delegate, or as an invited speaker. It may also be possible to have an information stand to disseminate information, e.g. fact sheets, etc.

Efforts carried out on a personal approach will help to VALKYRIES' success by building a network between people and institutions, forging relationships with interested parties with face-to-face meetings.

In Table 3, there is a list of events that have already taken place during the first 6 months of project.

Event	Date	Organizer	Description
ENISE (Spain)	19-20/10/2021	INCIBE	ENISE is the largest annual cybersecurity event in Spain. The project coordinator and the C&D Manager attended at the invitation of INCIBE, who signed a LoS. During the event, we disseminated VALKYRIES' project to key entities and actors of the cybersecurity industry that was present. https://www.incibe.es/enise
FEINDEF (Spain)	3-5/11/2021	IFEMA	FEINDEF bring the global defence and security sector together with the entire Spanish defence community to innovate, cooperate internationally and share knowledge, bringing together companies, organizations, universities and others as a global response to security challenges. The event was attended by the project coordinator and the C&D Manager, invited by CDTI to present the VALKYRIES project on a round table. https://www.feindef.com/conferencias.asp

Event	Date	Organizer	Description
AIMES Demo (Portugal)	17/12/2021	PARTICLE & HESE	The final pilot of AIMES H2020 project was successfully conducted and hosted by the Hospital do Espirito Santo de Evora (HESE) in the city of Évora, Portugal. HESE was available to host the pilot since they used the eCare solution, a core component of the demonstration. The focus of the final pilot was to demonstrate important PEMEA capabilities – including roaming, multimedia calls, file exchange and automatic translation – and the latest features developed in AIMES related to automated calls and incident dispatching. During this event the VALKYRIES SP-PT Use case was presented. https://aimes-eurostars.eu/event/aimes-final-pilot/
U.S.- Spain coffee chat	08/03/2022	U.S. Commercial Services	VALKYRIES project was presented in a round table together with Spanish National Police and the National Contact Point of CDTI to U.S SMEs and stakeholders. https://twitter.com/IndraCompany/status/1500897397962153986?s=20&t=DUPXNP4r4vd4QaHVS2PmHw

Table 3 - Conferences and events performed during the first 6 months

We also have defined a list of planned event for the next 6 months of Y1. These events are shown in Table 4.

Event	Date	Organizer	Description
CPDP Conference (Belgium)	23-25/06/2022	Consortium of Conference Partners	CPDP is a non-profit platform founded in 2007 and has now grown into a platform carried by 20 academic centers of excellence from the EU, the US and beyond. As a world-leading multidisciplinary conference CPDP offers the cutting edge in legal, regulatory, academic and technological development in privacy and data protection. CPDP gathers academics, lawyers, practitioners, policy-makers, industry and civil society from all over the world. This unique multidisciplinary formula has served to make CPDP one of the leading data protection and privacy conferences in Europe and around the world. https://www.cpdpconferences.org This event has been aligned with the 1 st Legal and Ethical VALKYRIES Workshop
XXXII SEMES National Congress	from June 8-10/06/2022	SEMES, Sociedad Española de Medicina de Urgencias y Emergencias	TASSICA EMERGENCY, TRAINING & RESEARCH S.A. and SUMMA112 will present several posters in this congress, informing about the objectives of the Valkyries project as well as the use-case 1

Table 4 - Conferences and events scheduled between M7-M12

In the second year of the project (Y2) the Consortium will try to participate in the events and conferences described in Table 2.

4.5. Key Performance Indicators of communication activities

The evaluation and progress of communication activities will be monitored by means of the following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). All activities, expected impact, target audiences and KPIs objectives are summarize in Table 5.

Activity	Description	Expected impact	Audience	KPIs
Design logo and presentation templates	Professional logo. Professional presentation template to be used by partners.	Visual identity and branding of the project; unified experience for the targeted audience.	All target audience groups.	Logo and templates available in professional quality by M2.
Project fact sheet	Double-sided A4 page containing basic information on the project.	Provision of instant information about the project.		500+ readers reached.
Project press releases and Newsletters	Showcase the progress and the results	Inform stakeholders, increase awareness and disseminate information		2+ newsletters per years 5+ Press releases per year
Project website	A website, providing information about the project, the demos and the results to target audiences.	Main online information point; communication of project news, events results; liaisons with other initiatives, projects through links.		An average of 500+ visitors per year.
Social Media channels	Regular sharing of news on activities and results as well as interaction with target audiences via social media.	Increasing visibility to stakeholders; direct communication mechanism between social media users and Consortium.		500+ followers on Twitter/LinkedIn 100+ tweets on Twitter 100+ Posts on LinkedIn.

Activity	Description	Expected impact	Audience	KPIs
White papers	Posters/banners to present the project's concept; Flyers with general project information; ad-hoc information at selected events.	Communication of results and information provision at events; ad-hoc diffusion of information based on identified opportunities.	End-users, Practitioners and institutions for regulation and standardization	2,000+ readers reached via printed and electronic copies.
Joint events, round tables	Events co-organized with targeted stakeholders or where VALKYRIES will be invited to present its work and vision.	Information exchange and dissemination; increase awareness.		500+ participants reached in total over 24 months
Demonstration, show cases, exhibitions	Events where VALKYRIES will communicate its results through demonstrations.	Attraction of target audiences and making them aware of the VALKYRIES solutions' benefits.		2,000+ visitors reached in total over 24 months

Table 5 - Summary of Communication activities and related KPIs

5. Dissemination Strategy

VALKYRIES will implement an integrated plan for effective dissemination of results which focus on pre-standardization, standardization and harmonization related activities. Although the dissemination plan is delivered as an outcome of task T1.4 Dissemination strategy, it considers three main objectives: i) create widespread awareness of the VALKYRIES solution and other project results among target audiences; ii) stimulate discussions and engagement with the pan-European and international Industry, Research and Technology Organisations (RTO), Certification and Testing Laboratories, Government/Regulatory Agencies, Military and General Public interested in the development and applicability of VALKYRIES and other results; iii) motivate target audiences to deploy VALKYRIES and other results commercially, and for further research and innovation. The table below (Table 6) presents the preliminarily identified audiences, Consortium interest, and contents/channel.

Audience	Main Objectives	Contents	Dissemination Channel
Industry, including associations and clusters	Raise awareness; generate interest; increase readiness to engage commercially; motivate their participation at regulatory and harmonization actions	Leaflets, newsletters, project presentations, posters, demos.	Trade shows, VALKYRIES workshops, conferences and exhibitions, public events, website, social media.
Certification and Testing Laboratories	Raise awareness; generate interest; increase readiness to adoption; motivate their participation at regulatory and harmonization actions	Leaflets, scientific papers, project presentations, posters, newsletters, demos	Private and public forums/events attended by emergency and first responder practitioners, VALKYRIES workshops, project demonstrations, website, social media
Regulation and Standardization	Raise awareness; generate interest; increase readiness to adoption; prompt related standardization, pre-standardization and harmonization actions; consider the VALKYRIES vision at cross-cutting standardization groups; motivate their participation at regulatory and harmonization actions	Leaflets, scientific papers, project presentations, posters, newsletters, demos	Private and public forums/events attended by emergency and first responder practitioners, VALKYRIES workshops, project demonstrations, website, social media.

Audience	Main Objectives	Contents	Dissemination Channel
End-users and disaster response practitioners	Raise awareness; generate interest; increase support for VALKYRIES; increase readiness for adoption and commercial engage; motivate their participation at regulatory and harmonization actions	Leaflets, newsletters, project presentations, posters, demos	Private and public forums/events attended by emergency and first responder practitioners, VALKYRIES workshops, project demonstrations, website, social media.
Military	Raise awareness; generate interest; increase support for VALKYRIES; motivate their participation at regulatory and harmonization actions	Project presentations, newsletters, demos.	Project demonstrations, VALKYRIES workshops, website, social media.
Private and public institutions/agencies in Europe	Raise awareness; generate interest; increase support for VALKYRIES; motivate their participation at regulatory and harmonization actions	Project presentations, newsletters, demos.	Project demonstrations, VALKYRIES workshops, website, social media.
Research and Technology Organisations (RTO). Academy	Raise awareness; generate interest; increase readiness; to engage in further; research based on VALKYRIES results; motivate their participation at regulatory and harmonization actions	Scientific papers and conferences, posters, reports, guidelines, protocols, project presentations, lectureships and academic symposiums.	Journals, workshops, conferences, website, social media.
Other related European projects and initiatives	Raising awareness; invitation to collaborate; presentation of results.	Leaflets, scientific papers, project presentations, posters, newsletters, demos.	Email, webinars, meetings, website, social media.

Table 6 - Identified audiences

To disseminate the VALKYRIES results to the defined target audiences, the VALKYRIES dissemination actions will take advantage of a set of channels best suited to each audience, including publications and events as we will see along the following sections.

The Consortium expects that different communities, working groups, EU initiatives, and stakeholders' groups (practitioners, regulation and standardization institutions, RTOs, academy, military, etc.), will be interested in the VALKYRIES outcomes (some of them enumerated in Table 7).

Entity	Main dissemination aspects
The European Joint Research Centre	European Joint Research Centre is the Commission's science and knowledge service to carry out research and provide independent scientific advice and support to EU policy.
Integrated Mission Group for Security	Open forum which brings together technology experts from Industry, SMEs, Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) and Academia.
European Organisation for Security	Represents the interests and expertise of MS involved in Security providing technology Solutions and Services from the different countries of the European Economic Area, representing more than 65% of the European Security Market and 2 million employees in Europe.
European Committee for Standardization	Public standards organization to foster the economy of EU in global trading, maintenance and distribution of coherent sets of standards and specifications.
International Electro-technical Commission	Worldwide organization for standardization comprising all national electro-technical committees (IEC National Committees). Prepares and publishes international standards for all electrical, electronic and related technologies.
Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers	The International professional association for Electronic Engineering and Electrical Engineering (and associated disciplines) that where members collaborate on world-changing technologies –from computing and sustainable energy systems to communications, healthcare, and more.
Security Technology Assessment Unit	Research towards the standardization and harmonisation of the protection of European networked infrastructures and hazardous industrial installations.
European Defence Agency (EDA)	EDA supports the Council and the Member States in their effort to improve the EU's defence capabilities for the Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP).
Red Cross/Red Crescent	The international humanitarian movement founded to protect human life and health, to ensure respect for all human beings, and to prevent and alleviate human suffering.
EU Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid	EC's department for overseas humanitarian aid and civil protection. It aims to save and preserve life, prevent and alleviate human suffering and safeguard the integrity and dignity of populations affected by natural disasters and man-made crises.
Computer Privacy and Data Protection	As a world-leading multidisciplinary conference CPDP offers the cutting edge in legal, regulatory, academic and technological development in privacy and data protection.

Entity	Main dissemination aspects
Big Data Value Association (BDVA)	Industry-driven international not-for-profit organisation with 200 members all over Europe. BDVA is the private counterpart to the EU Commission to implement the Big Data Value PPP program.
European Factories of the Future Research Association	Non-for-profit, industry-driven association. The key objective of EFFRA is to promote pre-competitive research on production technologies within the European Research Area by engaging in a public-private partnership with the EU called 'Factories of the Future.
SoBigData++	SoBigData++ is the European Integrated Infrastructure for Social Mining and Big Data Analytics to deliver a distributed, Pan-European, multi-disciplinary research infrastructure for big social data analytics, coupled with the consolidation of a cross-disciplinary European research community, aimed at using social mining and big data to understand the complexity of our contemporary. Its large international and multidisciplinary community focused on the legal and ethical aspects of most of the technologies developed/employed in VALKYRIES. SSA as a member of SoBigData++ will leverage its dissemination channels to disseminate VALKYRIES' results.
European Society for Emergency Medicine (EUSEM)	The European Society for Emergency Medicine (EUSEM) is a non-profit scientific organisation born in 1994 whose aim is to promote and foster the concept, philosophy and the art of emergency medicine throughout Europe. Its Disaster Medicine Section was officially established in Munich in September 2008.

Table 7 - Expected communities, working groups, EU initiatives, and stakeholders' groups interested in VALKYRIES outcomes

5.1. Project Workshops

The Consortium will organise the following VALKYRIES workshops (see Table 8) aimed at mobilising key stakeholders and promoting the exchange of ideas among stakeholders and the scheduling of follow-up actions. It is expected that they will also build an engaged community and lead to new business opportunities and related relationships between certification, regulation and standardization entities, end-user groups, academy/RTOs and industry.

Workshops will focus on a variety of topics, these will include (amongst others):

- VALKYRIES workshops
- Ethical/Legal workshops
- Standardization workshops
- Demonstration workshops

Feedback will be gathered from each of the workshops both from the Consortium (see Section 4.3.5 and [Annex B – Event Satisfaction Survey](#)) and from external experts. For the latest, a dedicated form is being created for each WS in order to collect opinions, advises and general feedback from experts about the project development. Engagement of the target communities and end-users in workshops will trigger discussions and encourage stakeholder participation in the development of recommendations, the identification of future collaborations and opportunities for new funding and investment programmes.

First VALKYRIES Workshop (M6)
<p>The first VALKYRIES workshop will take place at the end of the first year, to present the project's status and achievements (requirements, scope of the demonstrators, normalization plans, consultation strategy, terminology and semantics, pre-standardization map, etc.) and receive feedback from stakeholders to improve the impact of the final results, being taken into consideration when designing harmonization tactics and reference integrating the efforts to be conducted.</p> <p>Main objective: Present the VALKYRIES progress and its current outcomes to VALKYRIES stakeholders. Ask them for feedback and discuss expectations and possible exploitation approaches. The received suggestions shall enhance the VALKYRIES tasks to be conducted, settling the grounds for the rest of the project.</p>
Second VALKYRIES Workshop (M12)
<p>The second VALKYRIES workshop is scheduled at the end of the first year of the project, and will have as main target to disseminate the intermediate project outcomes and discuss the status and expectations from the reference integration; based on them, discuss with the present stakeholders the best suitable standardization and exploitation foreseen actions.</p> <p>Main objective: Present the intermediate outcomes of the VALKYRIES project to the different groups of stakeholders. Based on that, it will be possible to refine the ongoing reference integration and to enhance the direction of the initiated pre-standardization, standardization and harmonization actions.</p>
Third VALKYRIES Workshop (M24)
<p>The third VALKYRIES workshop is scheduled at the end of the project and will have as the main target to disseminate the final project outcomes, and based on them, discuss with the best and post-project exploitation opportunities.</p> <p>Main objective: Present the outcomes of the project to stakeholders. Based on that, it will make possible to better assess the impact in the invited communities and receive feedback about the planned final and post-project exploitation actions.</p>
Ethical-Legal VALKYRIES Workshops (M6, M12, M18, M24)
<p>These workshops will be organized to sensitize the ethical-legal framework in the VALKYRIES context and to discuss the progress on the development of protocols with stakeholders. The same workshop will be taken in VALKYRIES to reach the most comprehensive number of stakeholders.</p> <p>Main objective: Disseminate and discuss the VALKYRIES results on the ethical-legal issues and to discuss concrete regulatory solutions to standardization and interoperability goals regarding data and technology in the field of VALKYRIES disaster management scenarios.</p>
Standardization VALKYRIES Workshops (M6, M12, M18, M24)
<p>These workshops will be organized in parallel to the VALKYRIES' ethical-legal, closing the external stakeholders related to regulation, standardization, certification and harmonization to the Consortium activities. Their main targets will be to discuss the opportunities and progress on the actions mentioned above and getting close to the ongoing/planned Pan-European efforts (institutes, agencies, etc.) and working groups and end-users.</p> <p>Main objective: Disseminate and discuss VALKYRIES results on the regulation, standardization, certification and harmonization issues towards raise awareness of the project results and get alignment with European and International actions.</p>
Demonstration VALKYRIES Workshops (M6, M12, M24)
<p>These workshops will be organized in parallel to the VALKYRIES' Workshops, closing the external stakeholders related to security of European civil societies to the Consortium activities. Their main targets will be to discuss the definitions and development on the actions to be carried out for the final demonstration scenarios, getting close to working groups and end-users.</p> <p>Main objective: Disseminate and discuss VALKYRIES definitions on the demonstration scenarios issues towards raise awareness of the project results and get alignment with European and International actions..</p>

Table 8 - Project Workshops

5.2. Publication of the results

Results will be published in high impact scientific journals and on the VALKYRIES website. They will also be shared on LinkedIn and Twitter.

Project results will be shared with the EU Commission for publication on the European Commission channels such as Horizon magazine, Research*EU magazine, Research*EU Focus magazine and newsletters.

VALKYRIES partners will select the most appropriate journals and conferences to disseminate the results achieved. Table 9 provides an initial selection of targeted publications.

Publication	Main dissemination aspects
IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials	JCR IF: 20.2 (Q1). Disseminates tutorials and surveys covering all aspects of the communications field, with the purpose of adding understanding to the existing literature on communications, putting results in context.
IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing	JCR IF: 6.404 (Q1). Dependability and security, including the joint consideration of these issues and their interplay with system performance.
International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction	JCR IF: 2.896 (Q2). Fundamental and applied research, critical reviews, policy papers and case studies with a focus on multi-disciplinary research that aims to reduce the impact of natural, technological, social and intentional disasters.
Decision Support Systems	JCR IF: 4.71 (Q1). Foundations, functionality, interfaces, implementation, impacts, and evaluation of decision support systems.
Prehospital Emergency Care	JCR IF: 2.69 (Q2). International research relevant to the practice, educational advancement and investigation of emergency medical services.
Socio-Economic Planning Sciences	JCR IF: 4.14 (Q1). Operations research/management science, statistics, and related arenas, to in problems arising in socio-economic planning and development.
Energy	JCR IF: 5.537 (Q1). Covers research in mechanical engineering and thermal sciences, with a strong focus on energy analysis, energy modelling and prediction, integrated energy systems, energy planning and energy management.
Journal of Environmental Management	JCR IF: 4.865 (Q1). Publishes original research related to managing environmental systems and improving environmental quality, like system modelling and optimization, or social, economic and policy aspects.
Opinio Juris in Comparatione	Opinio Juris in Comparatione is an electronic open-access journal devoted to studies in comparative and national law. VALKYRIES will enquire about the legal aspects related to the enquired crisis management scenarios, taking advantage of the journal's international character and its openness to publication in several languages.
Safety Science	JCR IF: 4.105 (Q1). Physics and engineering of safety; its social, policy and organizational aspects; the assessment, management and communication of risks; effectiveness of control and management

Publication	Main dissemination aspects
	techniques for safety; standardization, legislation, inspection, insurance, costing aspects, human behaviour and safety.
International Data Privacy Law	JCR IF: 4.162 (Q1) Data protection and privacy law topics from around the world. This includes coverage in Europe (including the GDPR) and other regions such as Africa, Asia-Pacific, and the Americas, as well as at the international level.
Academic Emergency Medicine	JCR IF: 3.451 (Q1). Academic Emergency Medicine (AEM) is the official publication of the Society for Academic Emergency Medicine (SAEM) and publishes information relevant to the practice, educational advancements, and investigation of emergency medicine.
Resuscitation	JCR IF: 5.262 (Q1). Resuscitation is a monthly international and interdisciplinary medical journal. The papers published deal with the aetiology, pathophysiology and prevention of cardiac arrest, resuscitation training, clinical resuscitation, and experimental resuscitation research.
BMC Emergency Medicine	JCR IF: 2.119 (Q3). BMC Emergency Medicine is an open access, peer-reviewed journal that considers articles on all urgent and emergency aspects of medicine, in both practice and basic research. In addition, the journal covers aspects of disaster medicine and medicine in special locations, such as conflict areas and military medicine, together with articles concerning healthcare services in the emergency departments.

Table 9 - Selection of targeted publications

5.3. Individual Dissemination Strategies

The dissemination plan has required the review of local information, identification of stakeholders that enable the further development of the solutions, identification of funding sources and establishment of common requirements and replication strategies. Individual overview of main dissemination strategies per partner has been outlined in this section, summarised in Table 10.

End-Users
<p>SMS will contribute to make the project visible at regional, national and international levels, supporting dissemination strategy and attendance to at least 2 international major related events. SMS will present the project's results through devoted papers or posters, to disseminate VALKYRIES among the international community of first responders to emergency situations. Attendance to international conferences will be combined with local related events and showcases.</p> <p>List of events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NCT NCBNE Europe (http://nct-europe.com/) • FIRST Conference (https://www.first.org/conference/) • Annual SICUR fair (https://www.ifema.es/sicur) • European Society for Emergency Medicine (EUSEM) congress (https://eusem.org/) • European Emergency Medical Services (EMS) Congress (https://emseurope.org/) • Spanish Society of Emergency Medicine (SEMES) National conference • SERMAS-SUMMA112 information session on H2020 research projects
<p>BRC will spread information about results and good practices achieved by the Valkyries among professionals in the Red Cross and Red Crescent International Movement and International platforms and organizations BRC is part of. BRC will disseminate the results of VALKYRIES in its website and social media, as well as through its bi-weekly electronic bulletin, distributed to various media and stakeholders in Bulgaria. Specifically, the project results will be communicated with the National Civil</p>

Protection authority in Bulgaria (DG “Fire Safety and Protection of Population”) and with the NATO Centre of Excellence in Bulgaria. Internationally, the BRC will disseminate the project results within the Red Cross Red Crescent Movement, specifically among EU National Societies through the Red Cross Office in Brussels (at EU level events) and in the wider Europe region through the Regional Office of the International Federation of the Red Cross Red Crescent Societies in Budapest. Depending on the nature of project outcomes and their potential end-users, the project results may be disseminated in other international platforms and networks in which the BRC is a member or has cooperation with. These possibilities include the International Commission for Alpine Rescue (ICAR), International Life Saving Federation of Europe (ILSE), Disaster Preparedness and Prevention Initiative for South-Eastern Europe (DPPI SEE), etc.

HESE will create awareness of VALKYRIES relevance on interoperability and emergency response. HESE will disseminate the VALKYRIES results in relevant conferences and workshops, targeting the relevant VALKYRIES research areas related to the role of healthcare institutions in cross-border emergency response, including cooperation and information exchange. HESE will disseminate the results to Portuguese stakeholders directly involved in healthcare, security, safety and civil protection aspects. HESE will collaborate in the update of the content of the project’s official website. HESE aims to disseminate the project’s results and project achievements through the publication of at least 2 scientific peer reviewed papers in renowned security-related conference proceedings. Also, HESE plans the participation in 2 healthcare related events (exhibitions, fairs, workshops, meetings), involving an audience of more than 100 participants. In addition, HESE will support cross-fertilisation and networking activities between the Project and relevant initiatives in the emergency field, including those involving National and Regional Civil Protection Authorities and Ambulance Services. HESE will contribute to the project’s website and social media platforms. Finally, HESE will produce at least 3 blog entries associated with the Project that will be published in HESE official website.

List of events:

Peer-reviewed publications (journals, proceedings) and magazines:

1. Healthcare Informatics Research
2. The IOT Magazine
3. HealthTech

Events (conferences, workshops, meetings):

4. Portugal eHealth Summit
5. IOT Solutions World Congress

Networking and clustering:

6. Liaison (meetings) with National and Regional Civil Protection Authorities
7. Liaison (meetings) with Ambulance Services

AREU will disseminate the VALKYRIES results to Italian (particularly Lombardy) stakeholders involved in the healthcare and emergency response. This target will be reached with communication in relevant congress, conference, workshop and with publication in scientific literature as permitted. All the communication will be directed to people involved at a different level in healthcare, cooperation and emergency response.

HRT will share the project’s results with relevant stakeholders such as other rescue volunteer organizations and national rescue authorities like Hellenic Fire Brigade and EKAV (National EMS). HRT will disseminate the project through its social media accounts and its website. Additionally, HRT aims to disseminate the project in various national and international conferences in which the organization participates.

HRT is a member in ICAR and in IMRF and will support the dissemination of the project in the respective regional and international events.

Industry / SMEs

IND will disseminate VALKYRIES results in the trade fairs and relevant industrial/research conferences and committees it attends regularly. In the scientific domain, IND will participate in national, European and international congresses and conferences, workshops and seminars, forums and exhibitions, research journals and technical reports. On the other hand, in the area of establishing relationships with industrial stakeholders, research centers and academy, IND will promote the organization of

industrial workshops, seminars, as well as participation in lectures and master's courses to disseminate the results, identify new talent and generate innovation opportunities. Finally, IND also expects to participate in industrial forums more focused on data management and command and control (C2) techniques and methodologies on civil security, carrying out demonstrations and technical workshops about the results obtained during the project.

In the scientific domain, Indra will participate in national, European and international congresses and conferences; workshops and seminars; forums and exhibitions; research journals and technical reports. In the area of establishing relationships with industrial stakeholders, research centers and academy, Indra will promote the organization of industrial workshops, seminars, as well as participation in lectures and masters courses in order to disseminate the results, identify new talent and generate innovation opportunities. Finally, Indra also expects to participate in industrial forums more focused on security techniques and critical infrastructure protection, carrying out demonstrations and technical workshops about the VALKYRIES' project results.

List of events:

- DG ECHO events (Civil Protection Forum) and additional EC events (DG CLIMA, DG ENV, JRC)
- Research Workshops of the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies
- The International Emergency Management Society (TIEMS) events
- European Commission Community of User events
- European Civil Protection Forum
- Security Standardisation Research Conference
- International Disaster and Risk Conference (IDRC)
- International Conference on Preparedness & Response to Emergencies & Disasters
- Military Communications and Information Systems Conference (MilCIS)
- International Conference on Dependable Systems and Networks
- Computer Privacy and Data Protection (CDPD)
- SICUR
- SEGUREX
- MILIPOL PARIS

TAS will direct its dissemination strategy of VALKYRIES towards its two usual areas of influence in Spain, Central America, South America, seeking to reach those interest groups that can benefit or take advantage of its direct or future results: 1) Emergency services and professionals (especially doctors, nurses and emergency medical technicians). 2) Learning institutions (universities, colleges, training centres, etc.).

The dissemination actions by TASSICA SA will follow the entire life of the project. They will be planned and carried out according to the parameters established in the general dissemination plan of the project, regarding both communication activities and information that will be sent externally to interested parties. After the end of the project, dissemination actions related to the scientific exploitation of the data provided by the application of the project results would also be considered. The accessibility and data protection policy would always be within the terms established in the general plan of the project and that imposed by the laws in force in each case. Likewise, they will always be carried out ensuring adequate recognition of the source of EC funding in all communication and dissemination activities.

To achieve this, TAS will use, among others, the following channels and events: A) Seminars and conferences: both online and in-person, for communication of the project and its results. B) Congresses: presentation of the project results in national and international professional meetings related to emergencies. C) Professional and scientific publications: to promote the results of the project and to communicate the impact of the data derived from its application. D) Training actions: the study of the project and its results will be included in all the training programs of TAS related to emergencies or disasters. D) Corporate website and social networks: TAS' website and institutional profiles on Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and LinkedIn will be used to disseminate VALKYRIES to a wider audience.

EDGE will create awareness of VALKYRIES and EDGE solutions. EDGE aims to disseminate the VALKYRIES results and project achievements through the publication of at least 1 article in a security-related magazine. Also, EDGE plans the participation in 2 IoT, Health and Security-related events (exhibitions, fairs, workshops, meetings), involving an audience of more than 100 participants. Besides, EDGE will support cross-fertilisation and networking activities between the VALKYRIES Project and relevant

initiatives in the emergency field (e.g., Segurex in Portugal, Milipol in France). EDGE will contribute to the VALKYRIES project's website and social media platforms and will promote them to EDGE's contact network. Finally, EDGE will produce at least three blog entries associated with the VALKYRIES Project that will be published on the company's official website and social media pages.

List of events:

Peer-reviewed publications (journals, proceedings) and magazines:

1. Healthcare Informatics Research
2. The IOT Magazine
3. HealthTech

Events (conferences, workshops, meetings):

4. IEEE Conference on Connected Health: Applications, Systems and Engineering Technologies
5. Portugal eHealth Summit
6. IOT Solutions World Congress
7. the EENA Conference
8. SMI2G Brokerage Event

Networking and clustering:

9. Integrated Mission Group for Security (IMG-S)
10. PEMEA Network (pan-European Apps for citizens, <https://pemea.help/>)

NOV will carry out the dissemination of the ongoing actions and results of the VALKYRIES project in several ways:

1. Periodic informative releases will be made in the media and sectoral magazines (web and paper publications) related to the services sector and the industrial sector. Two publications per year are estimated on the objectives and progress of the VALKYRIES project and NOVOTEC's contribution to achieving these objectives, especially the objectives of harmonization and standardization of the proposed solutions.
2. Periodic posts will be made on NOVOTEC's LinkedIn profile (at least quarterly) to inform all stakeholders of the VALKYRIES project, its progress and NOVOTEC's contribution to achieving the project's objectives.
3. Informative emails about the project will be sent to NOVOTEC's client portfolio to publicize the project and find out the degree of interest that the VALKYRIES project may generate in other organizations.
4. Presentation documents of the VALKYRIES project will be made so that NOVOTEC can disseminate its objectives and goals in different forums or seminars that it can attend and that are related to the project's objectives.
5. Two webinars will be organized and promoted to disseminate the results of the use cases and the harmonization and standardization solutions proposed by the VALKYRIES project.

List of events:

- Standardization VALKYRIES Workshops (M6, M12, M18, M24)

BC2050 will disseminate the ongoing progress and project results of VALKYRIES by engaging in the following activities:

- Include the VALKYRIES project to its research-related website
- Include the VALKYRIES project in relevant company presentations
- Post news about the project in the company's websites
- Post news about the project in the company's social media
- Include information about the project in distributed newsletters

Other actions that are considered, but will be realized upon relevant arisen opportunities, which the company actively searches for:

- Presentation of VALKYRIES in workshops, infodays, and other similar events
- Dissemination of VALKYRIES progress and outputs in conferences
- Dissemination of VALKYRIES progress and outputs in the printed press

ARA will carry out the dissemination of the ongoing actions and results of the VALKYRIES project in the following ways:

1. Periodic informative releases will be made in the media and sectoral magazines (web and paper publications) related to the services sector and the industrial sector. Two publications per year are estimated on the objectives and progress of the VALKYRIES project and ARATOS' contribution to achieving these objectives, especially the objectives of harmonization and standardization of the proposed solutions.
2. Periodic posts will be made on ARATOS LinkedIn profile (at least quarterly) to inform all stakeholders of the VALKYRIES project, its progress and ARATOS contribution to achieving the project's objectives.
3. Informative emails about the project will be sent to ARATOS client portfolio to publicize the project and find out the degree of interest that the VALKYRIES project may generate in other organizations.
4. Presentation documents of the VALKYRIES project will be made so that ARATOS can disseminate its objectives and goals in different forums or seminars that it can attend and that are related to the project's objectives.
5. Two webinars will be organized and promoted to disseminate the results of the use cases and the harmonization and standardization solutions proposed by the VALKYRIES project

RTOs

UMU plans to disseminate the results obtained in VALKYRIES publishing them in venues with high scientific levels such as top journals and conferences. They will also be disseminated with local stakeholders with which UMU has a collaborative relationship regarding the transfer of research results from the University to private companies.

Among the planned activities UMU has detected the following:

- Publication in top journals and conferences as dissemination activities.
- Presentation of VALKYRIES results in workshops and EU events.
- Active participation in EU activities and working groups, especially the ones related to data privacy, cybersecurity, safety, and network management.

List of events:

IEEE Communications Magazine, IEEE Access, IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management, ACM Transactions on Privacy and Security, European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC).

SSA will include VALKYRIES outputs and methodologies in training activities and classes addressed to professionals and stakeholders, as well as courses and seminars addressed to undergraduates and PhD programs both in Law and Data Science. The developed protocols and guidelines will be adapted to other sectors for further technology transfer. SSA will disseminate the VALKYRIES output to a broader academic and professional audience with a workshop dedicated to the ethical, legal and societal aspects (ELSA) addressed in the project. SSA will also reach out to the broader public through periodic press releases and social media posts describing the progress of the project.

Planned activities:

- Incorporation in existing and new curricula
- *Opinio Juris in Comparatione* is an electronic open access journal devoted to studies in comparative and national law. VALYRIES will enquire the legal aspects related to the enquired crisis management scenarios, taking advantage of the journal's international character and its openness to publication in several languages.
- Ethical-Legal VALKYRIES Workshops (M6, M12, M18, M24) will be organised in order to sensitize on the ethical-legal framework in the VALKYRIES context and to discuss the progress on the development of the protocol within the stakeholders. The same workshop will be taken in VALKYRIES in order to reach the widest number of stakeholders
- Joint dissemination events with SoBIgData++, LEADS, ReCreating Europe (H2020 funded projects)

List of events:

- Special issue in *Opinio Juris in Comparatione* (international open access journal)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computer Privacy and Data Protection is the leading annual conference on privacy and data protection. VALKYRIES aims at regularly holding panels to publicly discuss its advances and main issues. • Ethical-Legal VALKYRIES Workshops (M6, M12, M18, M24)
<p>BDI will make the results from VALKYRIES project available policymakers, first responders and researchers in the EU MS and partner states. Professors and researchers in BDI are committed to develop and publish in peer-reviewed journals in the fields of Defence and Security Policy, Human Factors in defence and security, Cloud, IoT, Artificial Intelligence, and in general in ICT. Besides, BDI will use the Defence Science and Technology Journal (JDST), which is edited and published by the Institute to disseminate projects' results. Finally, BDI is going to communicate VALKYRIES results via yearly organised Military Technology & Science conference, by-annual HEMUS conference, publications in scientific journals, NATO Science and Technology Organisation and the European Defence Agency conferences and workshops, International Scientific yearly Conference Digital Transformation, Cyber Security and Resilience, etc.</p>
<p>KEM as a scientific, consulting and research agency for the Hellenic Ministry of Citizen Protection will bring and promote VALKYRIES scope, goals, objectives and results to the attention of several First Responders organisations supervised by the Ministry. These organisations are the Hellenic Police and its border Guard Directorate, the Fire Corps and the General Secretariat for Civil Protection. There are also several organisations interacting with the Ministry, such as local and regional Civil protection entities and NGOs. These affiliated organisations will also be informed about the achievements and outputs of VALKYRIES in several awareness events and practitioner events. In addition, KEMEA is appointed "National Contact Point" for the protection of European Critical infrastructures (ECIs) - "ECIP contact point". Therefore, the benefits of VALKYRIES will be disseminated to practitioners and other stakeholders operating and supporting Critical Infrastructures Facilities in Greece and other EU Member States.</p> <p>Finally, KEMEA is member in several Pan-European networks of practitioners and other actors in the field of security like ILEAD, FIRE-IN, EXERTER and the coordinator of MEDEA. Members of the networks will be informed about the research outcomes of VALKYRIES in a number of networking activities and events like the Community of Users and EU Security research event.</p> <p>Overall, the foreseen target dissemination group is comprised of First Responders' organisations, public and private security organisations, Disaster Relief NGOs, policy makers, members from the research and academia, policy makers and representatives from the industry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community of Users (CoU) annually events • Security Research Event (SRE) annually events • Industry days for First responders (IFAFRI Industry days) • Mediterranean Security Research Events • A number of clustering activities between the SEC-21-GM-2016-2017 - Pan European Networks of practitioners and other actors in the field of security • Networking activities between various H2020 projects. • EOS and EARTO meetings with focus on promoting PPDR technology advancements.
<p>USN offers a wide range of studies in both humanities, natural science and technology with a clear focus on technology for maritime operations., having direct cooperation with maritime authorities nationally as well as international, the first having laboratories and training centre locally The dissemination actions of USN will focus on sharing knowledge and teach relevant personal, assuming as typical target groups organizations and agencies involved in rescue and cleaning up operations on the sea. USN will teach courses at the university, both as a part of our running MSc and BSc activities and supplementary courses.</p>
<p>ISEMI will communicate and disseminate the activities of the project using own channels, which are organization's webpage and social media. At the same time, it will be subject of discussions during another institute's related projects (one of the mostly related one looks to be H2020 project RESCUER). Last, but not least, it will be included in information exchange within its advisory board and wide pool of experts, especially Slovak responders (IRS, FRS, police, civil protection...).</p>

Table 10 - Individual Dissemination strategies

5.4. Joint Dissemination Strategies

Apart from the individual dissemination plans described before, the Consortium has detected a set of joint dissemination actions that can be held or developed by two or more partners.

These activities include:

- **Round tables / joint conferences.** Since the VALKYRIES consortium is composed of research centres, end users and industrial partners the development of joint conferences will help to give different point of views and approaches about the project to the audience as well as increasing the opportunities of high-level discussions.
- **VALKYRIES demonstration scenarios.** The four demonstration scenarios that will be carried out at the end of the project are themselves joint dissemination activities since each of them involve several partners.
- **High impact papers.** Scientific papers written between two or more partners.

5.5. Liaisons with other projects and initiatives

One of the purposes of European projects is to carry out researches and developments that have an impact on the European community, so that projects such as VALKYRIES are not limited to the two-year total duration of the project. For this aim, it is of special importance to carry out activities of liaison with other projects under the same European framework (Horizon 2020). In this way, the consortium reviews ongoing or completed projects within a similar topic to detect synergy points and, ultimately, integration points between projects. The purpose is to maximize the efforts, discoveries and developments made by other consortiums trying to reuse lessons learned, designs or even developments that enhance the results of VALKYRIES.

The detected activities that could be done in order to stablish a liaison between projects are those listed below. All these proposed activities imply a different amount of effort and resources as shown in Figure 5.

- **Synergy points analysis.** Efforts to detect and analyse points of convergence between two or more projects and determine if they enhance their value.
- **Round tables / joint conferences.** Presenting both projects and the results obtained from the previous phase synergy points analysis.
- **High impact papers.** Scientific papers written between two or more partners.
- **VALKYRIES demonstration scenarios.** The four demonstration scenarios that will be carried out at the end of the project are themselves joint dissemination activities since each of them involve several partners.

Figure 5 - Proposal of liaison activities

Until now, the Consortium has identified some interesting European projects that can be taken into consideration for a liaison. These projects are summarized in Table 11.

Project	Coordinator	Framework	Reason of interest
UnCoVer	Institute of Tropical Medicine Antwerp	H2020	Efforts have been made in harmonization and pre-standardization of medical information located and distributed between European hospitals. https://www.uncoverproject.eu
ECYSAP	Indra	EDIDP	Ciber-situational awareness capabilities are crucial for the development and optimization of future critical emergency response situation. https://www.ecysap.eu/index.html
FIRE-RES	Centre de Ciència i Tecnologia Forestal de Catalunya	H2020	The project has strong synergies with VALKYRIES' Use Case 1. https://fire-res.eu
ANYWHERE	Universitat Politècnica De Catalunya	H2020	Enhance responder institutions and citizens anticipation and pro-active capacity of response to face extreme and high-impact weather and climate events through implementation of cutting-edge innovative technologies. http://anywhere-h2020.eu/
FASTER	The Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas (CERTH)	H2020	First responder Advanced technologies for Safe and efficient Emergency Response. FASTER addresses the challenges associated with the protection of first responders in hazardous environments, while at the same time enhancing their capabilities in terms of situational awareness and communication. https://www.faster-project.eu

Table 11 - Identified European projects for liaison

5.6. Key Performance Indicators of dissemination activities

The evaluation and progress of dissemination activities will be monitored by means of a list of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The KPIs objectives are summarize in Table 12.

Activity	Description	Expected impact	Audience	KPIs
VALKYRIES Workshops	VALKYRIES workshops in M6/M12/M24 will be organized.	Information exchange, dissemination; awareness.	End-users, Practitioners and institutions for regulation and standardization	3 workshops 30+ attendees per workshop. 25%+ of women per workshop
Legal / Ethical Workshops	L/E workshops in M6/M12/M18/M24 will be organized.	Sensitize the ethical-legal framework		4 workshops 15+ attendees per workshop. 25%+ of women per workshop
Standardization Workshops	workshops in M6/M12/M18/M24 will be organized.	Discussion of the VALKYRIES results on the regulation, standardization, certification and harmonization issues		4 workshops 15+ attendees per workshop. 25%+ of women per workshop
Demonstration Workshops	Demonstration workshops in M6/M12/M24 will be organised	Discussion of the VALKYRIES demonstration scenarios definition, planning and execution		3 workshops 30+ attendees per workshop. 25%+ of women per workshop
Liaisons	Liaisons with national and EU projects	Run liaison initiatives related with other H2020 projects to boost areas of application	EU H2020 Consortia	5+ liaisons with EU projects
Publications	Scientific and high-level publications	Contribute to scientific communities, dissemination; awareness	End-users, Practitioners and institutions for regulation and standardization	5+ Scientific publications with high impact 2+ Open access publications
Conferences	Scientific and high-level conferences	Contribute to scientific communities, dissemination; awareness		5+ Scientific Conferences with high impact
Experts involved	Stakeholders committed with external advisory boards	Receive impartial scientific advice, support the PST and advise the Consortium on social, environmental, technological,		5+ experts active involved per EAB

Activity	Description	Expected impact	Audience	KPIs
		legal and economic factors that may influence the innovation management of VALKYRIES		

Table 12 - Summary of Dissemination activities and related KPIs

6. Conclusions

Throughout this deliverable, a common strategy pursuing the accomplishment of communication and dissemination goals of VALKYRIES has been presented. The identification of primary stakeholders has underpinned a unified vision towards the planning of actions differentiating those relevant for the whole VALKYRIES consortium from the individual efforts drawn by the consortium members. Having in mind the agreed Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and the recognition of major stakeholders, the communication channels have been identified with the purpose of maximizing the visibility of the project to reach the targeted audiences effectively. As the communication in VALKYRIES is deeply recognized as a bidirectional process, a communication and dissemination strategies have been defined in line with the recommendations of the European Commission, which has the final goal to acquire feedback from the involved parties of the project ecosystem whilst ensuring the effective processing of the data and a seamless presentation of results. It led to outline the dissemination targets in line with the audiences the project intends to reach, boosting project impact through the most suitable communication channels. The actions described in this document shall be tracked throughout the project in deliverables D1.1 Periodic Management Report where the project impact will be evaluated, and the resulting goals presented within the periodic intermediate reports as the milestones concerning tasks T1.3 Consultation Strategy and Liaison with European/national authorities and T1.4 Dissemination strategy. At the time of this writing, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic is still struggling the regular course of actions in different aspects of our daily lives, being VALKYRIES not exempt from their side effects. As the consortium identifies likely events that might jeopardize the fulfilment of the dissemination objectives, the consortium will enforce the necessary adjustments to avoid compromising the project impact goals in the aftermath. All of them will be properly informed to the EC.

7. References

- [1] UN Environment OCHA Joint Unit Mission Report – 2005 China Petrochemical plant explosion. UNEP. <https://eecentre.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/China-december-2005-UNEP-Mission-Report.pdf>
- [2] Deep Water: The gulf oil disaster and the future of offshore drilling. National Commission on the BP Deepwater Horizon Oil Spill and Offshore Drilling. ISBN: 978-0-16-087371-3 (2011). <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/GPO-OILCOMMISSION/pdf/GPO-OILCOMMISSION.pdf>
- [3] La Palma volcano: Visual guide to what happened. BBC News. (2021) <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-58681233>
- [4] Ukrainian-Russian war. Russian forces "are bombing critical infrastructure," Ukraine's defense chief says. (2022) https://edition.cnn.com/europe/live-news/ukraine-russia-putin-news-03-05-22/h_b74ad770036da5436dd86b0095558bfc
- [5] https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm
- [6] https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm
- [7] <https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/horizon-magazine/battling-wildfires-behind-scenes>

8. Annex A – Documentation Management

8.1. Overview

The documentation management defines the process for preparation, identification, approval, edition, distribution, archive and control of the documentation of the project, document access and status of the documentation.

The Document Management System of the project will be an internal repository based on the **Microsoft SharePoint application**. The project has a private group on the platform, with INDRA as a tenant. All the Consortium partners have access to the group where all the documents elaborated in the project are stored.

The project repository can be found in the following link:

[Grp T H2020 VALKYRIES - Documents](#)

8.2. Documents formatting and version control

The deliverables will follow at least the rules specified below:

- Usage of the official VALKYRIES' templates
- Name and logo of the Consortium
- Document title and Reference number
- Date of the document
- Edition/Revision. The edition will be identified by a capital letter, starting with A. The letters "O", and "Ñ" will not be used
- The revision will be identified by a sequential number. A new revision will be set when minor changes after the official submission of the document. A new edition will be generated in the following cases:
 - if there are more than 5 revisions
 - If there are relevant modifications that affect most of the document
 - If new chapters are added
- Editors and contributors of the deliverable

8.3. Register of modifications

The date and the reason for change will be registered in the table of document changes record and the modifications will be indicated for the editions and the revisions.

The register is not applicable for the annexes that are separate documents with their own table of changes.

8.4. Control roles and register file

There is a document register file to record the documents generated during the project. Indra, as a coordinator and quality manager, will be responsible to update the document.

The register will contain the following information for each submission:

- Version
- Editor name and date: date and name of the person who prepares the document (from EDITOR partner)

- Reviewer name and date: date and name of the person with technical competence to review the document. It should be different from the person who prepares the document (from EDITOR partner)
- Coordinator name and date: date and name of the person with responsibility for the final authorization and release (INDRA)
- Quality name and date: date and name of the Quality Manager designated for the project (INDRA)
- Submission date

The document can be found in:

[Grp T H2020 VALKYRIES - Execution - Document Register \(sharepoint.com\)](#)

If new documents are to be created and added to the document register file, their codes must be requested to Indra, indicating the task to which they refer. Indra will supply the codes to the applicant.

8.5. Submission process of a new deliverable

Each deliverable has a defined Editor in the Grant Agreement. This editor will be responsible to create the document using the project template that can be found in:

[Grp T H2020 VALKYRIES - Templates \(sharepoint.com\)](#)

The chronology to issue the deliverable to the European Commission (EC) is as follows:

- **Step 0:** The document is edited and properly reviewed by the EDITOR PARTNER.
- **Step 1. At least three (3) weeks previous the date of issue of the deliverable:** the Editor of the document should deliver the reviewed document to the Project Coordinator (PC) for content evaluation in the following 3-4 days.
- **Step 2. At least two (2) weeks previous the date of issue of the deliverable:** the PC should deliver the document to the Quality Manager (QM) for inspection. If PC considers that major changes should be made on the content of the document it will be returned to the Editor in order to apply them in the following 2-3 days. Then the process should be restarted from step 1 having only 2-3 days to carry out the review by the PC and, as a consequence, reducing the QM' time of action. In order to reduce the risk of this happening, the PC will regularly check the progress of the document.
- **Step 3. At least one (1) week previous the date of issue of the deliverable:** Quality Manager sends the comments to the editor (if any) to be implemented. The editor will address the comments in the following 2-3 days.
- **Step 4. At least two (2) days previous the date of issue of the deliverable:** the Editor sends the document with quality comments implemented to the Project Coordinator.
- **Step 5.** The Project Coordinator (PC) will upload the document to the tender's portal of the EC.

		Week 3 before delivery					Week 2 before delivery					Week 1 before delivery				
		M	T	W	T	F	M	T	W	T	F	M	T	W	T	F
Step 1	E-PC															
Step 2	PC-QM															
Step 2*	PC-E															
	E-PC															
	PC-QM															
Step 3	QM-E															
Step 4	E-PC															
Step 5	PC-EC															

Figure 6– Chronology to issue a deliverable to the EC

8.6. Archive organization

The following table is an example of repository structure. This repository is under Sharepoint backup policies.

Repository	Directory	Content description
Grp_T_H2020_VALKYRIES	General	Documents of the tender phase
	Dissemination and Events	Templates, Consortium logo, newsletters, fact sheets, articles and publications
	Execution	Documents of the execution phase: deliverables, requirements, references, meeting information, etc
	Grant Agreement Channel	Contractual documents for Consortium Agreement and Grant Agreement
	Use Cases (ALL)	General and common documents for all use cases
	Use Case 1_SP PT	Documents regarding the preparation of Use Case 1
	Use Case 2_AT SK	Documents regarding the preparation of Use Case 2
	Use Case 3_BG GR	Documents regarding the preparation of Use Case 3
	Use Case 4_NO NL DK	Documents regarding the preparation of Use Case 4

Table 13. Directory of the project

8.7. Language and formats

The internal documents of the project and the deliverable documents will be written in English.

The documents will be done using MS Word, MS Excel or MS PowerPoint and will be published and delivered to the client in pdf format.

8.8. Project Documentation

The list of deliverable documents that will be generated during project execution is listed in Table 14. Other documents could be released if required.

ID	Title	WP	Editor	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D1.1	Periodic Management Report	WP1	INDRA	Report	Confidential*	M6, M12, M18, M24

ID	Title	WP	Editor	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D1.2	Financial Statements & Work Report	WP1	INDRA	Report	Confidential*	M12, M24
D1.3	Data Management Plan	WP1	SSSA	Open Research Data pilot	Confidential*	M6, M12, M24
D1.4	Protocol for Innovators	WP1	SSSA	Report	Public	M12, M24
D1.5	Data Management Platform	WP1	SSSA	Demonstrator	Public	M24
D1.6	Ethics and Diversity compliance Report	WP1	SSSA	Report	Public	M12, M24
D1.7	Consultation Strategy	WP1	INDRA	Report	Public	M1
D1.8	Covid-19 Protocol	WP1	INDRA	Report	Confidential*	M1, M6, M12, M18, M24
D1.9	Communication and Dissemination Strategy	WP1	INDRA	Report	Public	M6
D1.10	Impact Creation Reports	WP1	INDRA	Report	Public	M12, M24
D1.11	Dashboard	WP1	INDRA	Demonstrator	Public	M18
D2.1	Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases	WP2	INDRA	Report	Public	M5, M12
D2.2	Terminology and Semantics	WP2	TASSICA	Report	Public	M6
D2.3	Architecture Design Document	WP2	PARTICLE	Report	Public	M7, M12
D2.4	Map of Standards and joint roadmap	WP2	NOVOTEC	Report	Public	M5
D2.5	Harmonization framework	WP2	NOVOTEC	Report	Public	M12, M24
D2.6	Harmonization and Standardization Reports	WP2	NOVOTEC	Report	Public	M6, M12, M18, M24
D3.1	Report on relevant ethical-legal and societal aspects	WP3	SSSA	Report	Public	M12

ID	Title	WP	Editor	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D3.2	Report on the technical, legal, and ethical profiles related to the interoperability of first response capabilities	WP3	INDRA	Report	Public	M6, M12, M24
D3.3	Report on data protection and IP boundaries in the applicable framework	WP3	SSSA	Report	Public	M22
D3.4	Sustainable certification, conformity criteria and evaluation	WP3	USN	Report	Public	M6, M12, M24
D3.5	Business Cases	WP3	INDRA	Report	Public	M20
D3.6	Exploitation Plan	WP3	INDRA	Report	Public	M24
D4.1	Landscape of emerging technological opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters	WP4	UMU	Report	Public	M9, M18
D4.2	Harmonization opportunities on the technological landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters	WP4	UMU	Report	Public	M11, M18
D4.3	Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters	WP4	UMU	Report	Public	M18
D4.4	VALKYRIES harmonisations on first aid response technologies and equipment	WP4	UMU	Demonstrator	Public	M18

ID	Title	WP	Editor	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D5.1	Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters	WP5	TASSICA	Report	Public	M9, M18
D5.2	Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters	WP5	TASSICA	Report	Public	M11, M18
D5.3	Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters	WP5	TASSICA	Report	Public	M18
D5.4	VALKYRIES harmonization on first aid response common practices and procedures	WP5	TASSICA	Demonstrator	Public	M18
D6.1	Landscape of emerging preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters	WP6	BDI	Report	Public	M9, M18
D6.2	Harmonization opportunities on the preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters	WP6	BDI	Report	Public	M11, M18

ID	Title	WP	Editor	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D6.3	Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters	WP6	BDI	Report	Public	M18
D6.4	VALKYRIES harmonisations on first aid preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration	WP6	BDI	Demonstrator	Public	M18
D7.1	Testbeds and Evaluation Methodology	WP7	KEMEA	Demonstrator	Public	M10
D7.2	Datasets Management and Benchmarking	WP7	UMU	Demonstrator	Public	M24
D7.3	System Validation and Evaluation	WP7	INDRA	Report	Public	M18
D7.4	VALKYRIES Reference Integration and lessons learned	WP7	ARATOS	Report	Public	M21
D7.5	Report of the use case: Spain-Portugal	WP7	SERMAS	Demonstrator	Public	M24
D7.6	Report of the use case: Slovakia-Austria	WP7	ISEMI	Demonstrator	Public	M24
D7.7	Report of the use case: Bulgaria-Greece	WP7	BDI	Demonstrator	Public	M24
D7.8	Report of the use case: Norway-Netherlands	WP7	USN	Demonstrator	Public	M24
D8.1	H - Requirement No. 1	WP8	INDRA	Ethics	Confidential*	M6
D8.2	H - Requirement No. 2	WP8	INDRA	Ethics	Confidential*	M9
D8.3	POPD – Requirement No. 3	WP8	INDRA	Ethics	Confidential*	M6
D8.4	DU - Requirement No. 4	WP8	INDRA	Ethics	Confidential*	M9

ID	Title	WP	Editor	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D8.5	M - Requirement No. 5	WP8	INDRA	Ethics	Confidential*	M9
D8.6	EPQ - Requirement No. 6	WP8	INDRA	Ethics	Confidential*	M15

Table 14. List of deliverables

**only for members of the consortium will have access (including the Commission Services)*

8.9. Distribution

All the documents will be stored in the project Sharepoint group and delivered by the project coordinator to the client by using the Tender's Portal platform to manage the EU Grants.

9. Annex B – Event Satisfaction Survey

EVENT SATISFACTION SURVEY

Name of the event

Thanks for attending the event. We will use this questionnaire to make future events better, so please share your thoughts with us. This survey is completely anonymous. Thank you for your collaboration.

For the answers use the scale (one - five) 1-5, noting that 1 (one) = not satisfied and 5 (five) = very satisfied.

1. Were all the issues to be discussed covered?

1 2 3 4 5

2. How satisfied were you with:

a. The organization of the event

1 2 3 4 5

b. The event duration

1 2 3 4 5

c. The time management of the event?

1 2 3 4 5

d. The partners' participation and commitment with the event.

1 2 3 4 5

e. The partners' preparation for the event

1 2 3 4 5

3. Overall, how productive do you think the meeting was?

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

Aspects to improve:

Positive aspects of the event:

10. Annex C – Glossary

Acronym	Description
AEM	Academic Emergency Medicine
AES	Asociación Española de empresas de Seguridad
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
C2	Command & Control
CDTI	Centro para el Desarrollo Tecnológico Industrial
CPDP	Computer Privacy and Data Protection
CSDP	Common Security and Defence Policy
CV	Curriculum Vitae
DX.X	Deliverable X.X
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EDA	European Defence Agency
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
ELSA	Ethical, Legal and Societal Aspect
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
EU	European Union
EUSEM	European Society for Emergency Medicine
EUSEM	European Society for Emergency Medicine
FR	Funding Requirement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IA	Innovation Action
IDRC	International Disaster and Risk Conference
IHL	International Humanitarian Law
IoT	Internet of Things
JCR IF	Journal Citation Reports Impact Factor
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
L/E	Legal / Ethical
LoS	Letter of Support
MilCIS	Military Communications and Information Systems
MS	Member States
MX	Month X.X
PST	Program Steering Team
PT	Portuguese
PU	Public
QX	Quartil X
R	Report
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations
SAEM	Society for Academic Emergency Medicine
SEMES	Sociedad Española de Medicina de Urgencias y Emergencias
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SP	Spanish

Acronym	Description
TIEMS	The International Emergency Management Society
TX.X	Task X.X
U.S.	United States
WP	Work Package
WS	Workshops
YX	Year X

Table 15 - Glossary